

Classifying Dwarf Planets as Planets without Violating the IAU's Current Definition

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Abstract

The International Astronomical Union's (IAU) definition of a planet remains ambiguous due to the lack of a clear, quantitative specification for the 'clearing the neighborhood' criterion in Resolution B5. Thus we propose a new definition of planets so that it can be applied to all spherical bodies, covering exoplanets as well as planets within our solar system. This new definition aims to resolve the limitations of the current IAU framework.

1 Introduction

The International Astronomical Union (IAU) defines a planet as a body that orbits the Sun, achieves hydrostatic equilibrium, and clears its orbital neighborhood. The last criterion, an orbital clearing, has been formalized by many authors. Stern and Levison [5] introduce a dynamical parameter Λ , Soter [4] proposes a parameter μ , and Margot [2] presents a general formulation that yields a discriminant Π .

Here, we propose a new definition of a planet. In the definition, A planet must be greater than P_i of any other objects.

2 Existing Metric

Tremaine [6] develops the formation of Oort-type comet clouds, considering that the ejection of comets by the mass of a single planet is M_p , the semi-major axis a_p , and the mass of the central star M_* . The ejection process is a diffusion or random walk process in the orbital energy of a comet, with the energy described by the variable $x = 1/a$, where a is the semi-major axis of the comet's orbit. The diffusion coefficient $D_x = \langle(\Delta x)^2\rangle^{1/2}$ is the root mean squared change in x per orbit, resulting from the gravity kicks of an associated planet. Tremaine [6] finds that

$$D_x = \frac{10 M_p}{a_p M_\star} \quad (1)$$

and t_{diff} is

$$t_{diff} = P \frac{x^2}{D_x^2} \quad (2)$$

Later, Margot [2] argues that the clearing timescale should be a main sequence lifetime. However, Margot et al. [3] argues that the timescale based on a main-sequence lifetime of hydrogen-fusing stars must be abandoned and defines the clearing mass is

$$m_{clear} = C^{3/2} m_{central}^{5/8} \left(\frac{t_{clear}}{1.1 \times 10^5 y} \right)^{-3/4} a^{9/8} \quad (3)$$

3 Proposed Metric

Here, we propose new definition of a planet. v_{esc} in the distance of C hill radii is:

$$v_{esc} = \sqrt{\frac{2Gm_p}{CR_H}} \quad (4)$$

Hill radii R_H is:

$$R_H = a \left(\frac{m_p}{3M_{central}} \right)^{1/3} \quad (5)$$

orbital velocity difference Δv_{orb} is:

$$\Delta v_{orb} = \sqrt{\frac{GM_{central}}{a}} - \sqrt{\frac{GM_{central}}{a + CR_H}} \approx \frac{1}{2} C \left(\frac{m_p}{3M_{central}} \right)^{1/3} \sqrt{\frac{GM_{central}}{a}} \quad (6)$$

In Equation 6, a planet must be $v_{esc} > \Delta v_{orb}$ to capture or pull neighbourhood and C must be 1 because the object will be captured if any object comes within a hill radii.

4 Proposed Improvements to IAU Resolution B5 (2006)

Because it is relatively straightforward to apply a quantitative orbit-clearing criterion to exoworlds, it is possible to extend the 2006 IAU planet definition to brown dwarfs and stars other than the Sun and to remove ambiguity about what it means to clear an orbital zone. Likewise, it is possible to use a specific mass threshold to replace a vague and impractical prescription regarding roundness. We hope that these considerations will help start the conversation about making planetary taxonomy both quantitative and useful. One possible IAU-aligned formulation is as follows:

A planet is celestial body that

- (a) orbits one or more stars, brown dwarfs, stellar remnants;
- (b) has a true mass below the limiting mass for thermonuclear fusion of deuterium (currently calculated to be 13 Jupiter masses for objects of solar metallicity);
- (c) has a mass ratio with the central object below the L4/L5 instability i.e., $m/m_{central} < 0.04$;
- (d) $v_{esc} - \Delta v_{orb}$ is more than 0.

In this formulation, clause (c) follows the recommendations from the working definition of IAU Commission F2 (Lecavelier des Etangs and Lissauer [1]).

5 Conclusions

Precise definitions are needed to communicate and organize thoughts. The IAU definition of “planet” has been criticized with good reason since 2006. In this work, we examined the results of Solar System bodies to propose this definition. This analysis revealed the presense of groupings among Solar System bodies.

6 Acknowledgments

We thank to Lecavelier des Etangs and Jack Lissauer for helping us think about this definition.

References

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A New Planets in the Solar System

According to this new definition, planets would be Mercury, Venus, Earth, Mars, Ceres, Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus, Neptune, Orcus, Pluto, Haumea, Quaoar, Makemake, Gonggong, Eris, Sedna, and all exoplanets.

Name	Semi-major axis (AU)	Diameter (km)
Mercury	0.39	4880
Venus	0.72	12100
Earth	1.00	12700
Mars	1.52	6780
Ceres	2.77	950
Jupiter	5.20	139800
Saturn	9.54	116500
Uranus	19.20	50700
Neptune	30.13	49200
Orcus	39.17	910
Pluto	39.48	2370
Haumea	43.12	1630
Quaoar	43.69	1110
Makemake	45.50	1430
Gonggong	66.90	1230
Eris	67.99	1160
Sedna	506	600

Table 1: New Planets in the Solar System